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Geophysical and physicochemical investigation for Groundwater assessment: A case study of Abdullahi Fodio University of Science and Technology, Aliero Nigeria.

U. Z. Magawata^{1*} M. M. Lawal¹

¹Department of Physics

Abdullah Fodio University of Science and Technology, Aliero Nigeria

*Corresponding author email; zayyanu.magawata@ksusta.edu.ng

ABSTRACT

Groundwater is the principal source of potable water in northwestern Nigeria, yet it remains vulnerable to contamination from both natural and anthropogenic activities. This study assessed groundwater quality and potential heavy metal contamination within Abdullahi Fodio University, Aliero, Northwestern Nigeria, by integrating geophysical and hydrochemical approaches. Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) point and Very Low Frequency Electromagnetic (VLF-EM) traverse were employed across 13 locations to delineate aquifer zones and identify possible contaminant pathways. In addition, 10 water samples, 5 from shallow hand-dug wells and 5 from boreholes, were analyzed for physicochemical parameters and heavy metal concentrations using standard WHO, APHA, and EPA protocols. The geophysical surveys revealed heterogeneous subsurface conditions, with low-resistivity and high-conductivity zones interpreted as fractured and saturated formations that may act as contaminant migration pathways, particularly around VES 1–7, 11, and 12. However, VES 9, 10, and 13 indicated relatively resistive zones that a borehole can be drill. Hydrochemical analysis showed that zinc, cadmium, copper, and chromium remained within permissible limits, high levels of iron (up to 12.1 mg/L), lead (up to 0.189 mg/L), and arsenic (2.8–3.3 mg/L) were detected across borehole and reservoir samples exceeding WHO standards. Physiochemical parameters such as turbidity, chloride, and biochemical oxygen demand were generally higher in reservoirs than in boreholes, suggesting greater vulnerability of shallow systems to surface contamination.

Keywords: Groundwater, contamination, heterogeneous subsurface, Hydrochemical, Physiochemical parameters

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Groundwater is a crucial source of potable water in Nigeria, particularly in semi-arid regions such as the Sokoto Basin. Many communities in sub-Saharan Africa rely on privately owned wells of varying depths. These water sources are often vulnerable to contamination due to inadequate well construction, proximity to pollution sources, and insufficient protective measures. Contaminants migrate through vertical and lateral distances, influenced by geological formations, land topography, surface runoff, and hydrological conditions (Chidimba & Nfor, 2020; Yusuf et al., 2021). Understanding these contamination pathways is vital for implementing effective water resource management and pollution control strategies (Ezeh et al.,

2020; Hassan et al., 2022). Population growth, urbanization, and climate variability have escalated the demand for water resources, necessitating systematic hydrogeological investigations for sustainable management (Olorunfemi & Fasuyi, 1993). Among the widely used methods in groundwater exploration, subsurface structural integrity investigation, electrical resistivity surveys and water quality analyses help assess aquifer properties and groundwater suitability for consumption (Usman, 2019; Afolabi et al., 2020; Olanunmi et al., 2023; Olatunji, et al., 2025). The Sokoto Basin, part of the larger Iullemeden Basin, comprises lithological units such as the Gwandu, Rima, Sokoto, and Gundumi formations, which significantly influence groundwater occurrence and movement (Uma & Kehinde, 1994). Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) has been successfully employed in regions like Kebbi State to delineate aquifer zones, groundwater contamination, and assess groundwater potential (Ariyo & Banjo, 2008).

However, hydrochemical analysis for trace element concentration and other microbiological effects is essential for the exact determination of groundwater contamination, and it corroborates the results of mechanical alteration in soil and leachate (Aziz et al. 2010; Ayolabi et al. 2015; Fatta et al. 1999; Xing et al. 2013; Kamble et al. 2020; Farzaneh et al. 2021; Igboama et al. 2021).

Water quality analysis is essential in groundwater studies to determine the chemical composition, suitability for consumption, and potential contamination risks. Some key parameters analyzed include pH level, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), heavy metals, and microbial contaminants (Obiefuna & Orazulike, 2010; Farzaneh et al., 2021; Igboama et al., 2021; Olanunmi et al., 2023). The groundwater quality in the Sokoto Basin is influenced by rock-water interactions, agricultural activities, and industrial effluents, with some areas showing elevated concentrations of iron (Fe), fluoride (F⁻), and nitrates (NO₃⁻), which pose potential health risks (Ayinla et al., 2017). Previous studies have raised concerns about groundwater contamination from anthropogenic and natural sources, such as excessive fluoride levels leading to dental and skeletal fluorosis (Edet & Teme, 2004) and microbial contamination from poor waste management (Waziri & Ogali, 2021). In Kebbi State, groundwater contamination from agricultural fertilizers and pesticides has necessitated improved land and water management practices (Bashir et al., 2020). Despite studies focusing on groundwater potential and microbial contamination in Aliero (Magawata et al., 2020; Kalpana et al., 2011; Elinge et al., 2011), there remains a research gap regarding direct comparisons of borehole and dug well water quality within the university. This study integrates geophysical methods with water quality analysis to assess groundwater resources, determine suitability for human consumption, and identify potential health risks. Given the growing population of the historic rural settlement of Aliero, which hosts Abdullahi Fodio University of Science and Technology, proactive, preventive, and remedial strategies are necessary to safeguard groundwater quality and mitigate contamination risks that serve as the primary water source for students and staff.

1.1 Geological setting of the area

Aliero town is located within the Gwandu Formation and is part of the Sokoto Basin, a sedimentary basin in northwestern Nigeria. The Gwandu Formation is composed predominantly of continental sediments, including sandstones, clays, and lateritic deposits, which were deposited during the Paleogene period (Fig. 1). This formation is a significant aquifer system, providing groundwater to various communities, including Aliero. The lithology of the formation is characterized by moderate to high porosity and permeability, making it a crucial groundwater reservoir (Uma & Kehinde, 1994). Hydrogeologically, the Gwandu Formation consists of fine- to coarse-grained sandstones interbedded with clay layers. These characteristics influence groundwater recharge, storage, and movement. The presence of lateritic crusts and iron-rich deposits in some areas affects groundwater chemistry, leading to variations in water quality. The formation is formed by weathering and fracturing, which enhance secondary porosity and permeability, facilitating groundwater flow. Studies have shown that groundwater in the region is often confined to semi-confined conditions, with aquifers occurring at varying depths, typically between 20 and 80 meters (Ariyo & Banjo, 2008).

Figure 1. Geological map showing the study area

2.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study Area and Sample Collection

The study was conducted in Aliero, Kebbi State, focusing on groundwater sources around the designated study area. Six (6) water samples are collected, three (3) from shallow hand-dug wells (approximately 3 meters deep) and three (3) from boreholes (above 50 meters deep). The water samples were obtained near a potential contamination site to assess groundwater quality variations.

The hand-dug well water samples were labeled as:

Each sample was collected using sterilized polyethylene bottles to prevent contamination.

2.1.1 In-Situ Measurements

On-site (in-situ) measurements were taken to evaluate essential water quality parameters, including temperature, turbidity, electrical conductivity, appearance, odor, and taste. These preliminary assessments provided insights into potential contamination indicators.

2.1.2 Sample Preservation and Transportation

Water samples were preserved and transported in accordance with the American Public Health Association (APHA, 2005) standards. Samples were stored in ice-cooled containers and transported to the laboratory to prevent changes in chemical composition before analysis.

2.1.3 Laboratory Analysis

The laboratory analysis included a range of physical, chemical, and microbiological tests to assess groundwater quality. The following methods were applied:

pH Measurement: The hydrogen ion concentration (pH) of the water was determined using a calibrated pH meter, indicating its acidity or alkalinity.

Gravimetric Method: Applied to estimate total dissolved solids (TDS) and sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) concentrations.

Eriochrome Indicator Method: Used to measure total hardness (TH) and calcium hardness, from which magnesium hardness was calculated.

Iodometric Titration: Conducted to measure dissolved oxygen (DO) after 7-day incubation in a dark environment.

Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS): Utilized to detect and quantify heavy metals, including arsenic (As), cadmium (Cd), copper (Cu), chromium (Cr), iron (Fe), lead (Pb), and zinc (Zn) after sample digestion.

2.2 Data Analysis and Interpretation

The collected data were statistically analyzed to identify variations in groundwater quality between boreholes and hand-dug wells. The results were compared with national and international water quality standards to determine their suitability for human consumption. Furthermore, GIS-based mapping techniques were used to visualize spatial distribution patterns of groundwater contamination, assisting in the identification of high-risk zones and informing future groundwater management strategies.

In conducting water quality analysis in the laboratory, standardized methods prescribed by the WHO, EPA, and APHA ensure accuracy and reliability. pH measurement is performed using a calibrated pH meter, with WHO recommending a range of 6.5–8.5, while EPA and APHA follow similar protocols, ensuring calibration with buffer solutions. Temperature is measured using a digital or glass thermometer immediately after sample collection to avoid environmental influence. Electrical conductivity (EC) is determined using a conductivity meter, with compensation for temperature variations. Turbidity is analyzed with a Nephelometric Turbidity Meter (NTU meter), ensuring compliance with drinking water standards. Total dissolved solids (TDS) are measured using a gravimetric method by filtering and evaporating the sample at 180°C , while chloride (Cl^-) concentration is assessed through argentometric titration using silver nitrate. Sulfate (SO_4^{2-}) levels are determined via turbidimetric or ion chromatography methods.

For dissolved oxygen (DO), the Winkler titration method is widely used, with the WHO recommending a minimum of 5 mg/L for drinking water. Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) was determined using the 5-day incubation method (BOD_5) at 20°C , measuring the decrease in oxygen levels over time. Water hardness, primarily due to calcium (Ca^{2+}) and magnesium (Mg^{2+}), is analyzed through EDTA titration, using Eriochrome Black T as an indicator. Heavy metal contamination, including lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), iron (Fe), zinc (Zn), copper (Cu), chromium (Cr), and arsenic (As), is detected using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS), with strict limits enforced by WHO, EPA, and APHA. Each of these methodologies ensures compliance with regulatory standards, maintaining safe drinking water and environmental monitoring practices.

2.3 Data collection

Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) and Very Low Frequency (VLF) methods are widely used geophysical techniques for subsurface investigations, particularly in groundwater exploration. In the field, VES data collection involves selecting survey locations based on geological and hydrological conditions. A resistivity meter, such as an ABEM Terrameter, is used with electrode configurations like the Schlumberger or Wenner array. Current electrodes (A and B) are progressively spaced further apart while potential electrodes (M and N) remain closer together. A direct current (DC) is injected into the ground, and the resulting voltage is measured to calculate apparent resistivity at various depths. Each VES station is documented with GPS coordinates and relevant field notes to ensure accurate data interpretation.

VLF data collection, on the other hand, utilizes electromagnetic waves in the 15–30 kHz frequency range. A VLF receiver, such as the ABEM Wadi, is set to a transmitting station frequency, and readings are taken at regular intervals along a profile. The instrument measures tilt angle (in-phase) and quadrature (out-of-phase) responses, which help identify conductive subsurface structures. This method is particularly effective in detecting fractures, fault zones, and groundwater-bearing formations.

After field data acquisition, software tools are used for analysis and interpretation. VES data is processed using software such as IPI2Win. The collected apparent resistivity values and electrode spacing are entered into the software, and curve matching techniques are applied to estimate subsurface layer resistivity and thickness. One-dimensional inversion models are generated to visualize subsurface conditions and classify lithological units for groundwater potential assessment. For VLF data analysis, software such as KHFILT, NOTEPAD is used. The raw data undergoes Fraser and Karous-Hjelt filtering to enhance conductivity anomalies. By integrating VES and VLF results, a comprehensive hydrogeological model can be developed, improving the accuracy of groundwater exploration and facilitating the identification of possible contamination and subsurface characterization.

3.0 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Vertical electrical sounding (VES) result

The Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES) investigation conducted across thirteen locations reveals significant subsurface resistivity variations that correspond to different lithological units and highlight potential zones of groundwater contamination. These resistivity anomalies are primarily linked to low-resistivity layers, particularly within fractured basement zones that may serve as conduits for leachate migration from anthropogenic sources such as refuse dumps, septic tanks, or agricultural runoff. VES 1 (Admin Block) presents an H-type curve characterized by a low-resistivity second layer (182 Ωm), suggesting a water-saturated or clay-rich fractured basement at around 24 meters depth, potentially impacted by surface-derived contaminants. Similarly, VES 2 (Faculty of Physical Science 1) shows an HA-type curve with a significantly thick second layer (165 Ωm), pointing to a conductive layer that may represent a weathered and contaminated zone within the subsurface, likely affected by nearby academic and domestic activities. VES 3 (Faculty of Physical Science 2) also exhibits an H-type curve, where the second layer (172 Ωm) suggests a moderate depth, potentially a leachate-influenced zone, which could serve as a migration path for contaminants due to its conductive properties. VES 4 (Faculty of Life Science 1) features an HA-type curve with a second-layer resistivity of 179 Ωm , interpreted as a saturated or contaminated fractured zone, which could act as a conduit for downward contaminant transport. Likewise, VES 5 (Faculty of Life Science 2) presents an AA-type curve, and its low-resistivity third layer (190 Ωm) suggests the presence of a weathered basement that may be influenced by percolating contaminants. VES 6 and VES 7 (Faculty of Engineering 1 and 2) display QH-type curves, where second-layer resistivity of 148.3 Ωm and 172 Ωm , respectively, indicate zones of moisture retention or clay presence, both of which are common in leachate-affected areas. These intermediate-depth conductive zones may reflect the presence of contamination pathways within fractured rock or saturated overburden. VES 8 (Junior Staff Quarters 1) reveals an A-type curve with a notably high second-layer resistivity of 1190 Ωm . Although such high values typically suggest dry, resistive lithologies, this anomaly may also be attributed to ionic enrichment or mineralized zones, necessitating further investigation to determine whether it represents geological variation or subsurface contamination. In contrast, VES 9 (Junior Staff Quarters 2) displays a QQ-type curve, and VES 10 (Male Hostel) features an HA-type curve, both of which show consistently high resistivity layers across the depth profile, indicating dry, unfractured subsurface conditions that are likely free of contamination. These areas can be considered low-risk zones with minimal vulnerability to leachate infiltration. VES 11 (Female Hostel) is characterized by a QH-type curve and a low second-layer resistivity of 127 Ωm , interpreted as a leachate-bearing fractured zone. This suggests the presence of a conductive layer likely influenced by moisture or contaminants, especially given the proximity of domestic waste sources. Similarly, VES 12 (Faculty of Agriculture 1) shows a KH-type curve with a third-layer resistivity of 194 Ωm , suggesting a deep fractured basement zone that may have been infiltrated by leachate or other pollutants, potentially from agricultural activities or surface drainage. On the other hand, VES 13 (Faculty of Agriculture 2) exhibits an HK-type curve with generally high resistivity values, indicating a dry, resistive subsurface composed of unfractured and uncontaminated materials, thereby reflecting a low vulnerability to groundwater pollution.

3.2 Very low frequency (VLF EM) result

The interpretation of VLF data across thirteen traverses using Fraser and Karous-Hjelt filtering techniques reveals significant subsurface conductivity variations with implications for groundwater contamination. Traverse One (Admin Block) shows zones of high conductivity between 100–150 meters, with real component values ranging from -60 to -30, suggesting water-saturated formations such as clays or shallow aquifers (Fig. 2a). These conductive areas align with strong negative Fraser responses (-150% to +200%), highlighting potential contaminant migration paths, especially near sources like septic tanks or waste dumps. Resistive zones at the start of the traverse may act as natural barriers against infiltration. In Traverse Two (Faculty of Science), conductive anomalies are identified between 80–160 meters at depths of 10–30 meters, with real component values also between -60 and -30. Fraser filtering supports this with negative spikes around 100 and 200 meters, suggesting saturated or clay-rich layers that can facilitate contaminant movement (Fig. 2b). High positive Fraser values may indicate more resistant and safer zones. Traverse Three (Faculty Science 2) shows evidence of possible subsurface contamination based on both Fraser and Karous-Hjelt filtering results. The Fraser filtering graph reveals sharp fluctuations, with strong negative and positive anomalies, particularly a significant dip near 200 m, indicating high subsurface conductivity, which may suggest contamination or fluid saturation. The Karous-Hjelt pseudo-section supports this, showing low resistivity zones (blue to black) between 40–80 m and around 200 m, likely representing leachate zones or water-saturated fractures (Fig. 2c). Similarly, the central portion of the section (90–180 m) shows high resistivity (red to orange), indicating drier, uncontaminated materials. Traverse Four reveals a significant conductive zone between 90–140 meters, interpreted as a vertically extensive contaminant plume (Fig. 2d). The Karous-Hjelt section displays deep blue and cyan hues, while Fraser filtering shows strong negative responses and sharp lateral contrasts, particularly around 110–130 meters. Additional oscillations between 190–270 meters suggest heterogeneity in subsurface materials, with the 90–140 meter segment identified as most vulnerable. Traverse Five presents a strong positive Fraser anomaly above 300% at the start, dropping sharply below zero around 50 meters, and then stabilizing. Traverses 5 to 13 (Figs. 2e to 2m), were presented in appendix 1 to 3. The Karous-Hjelt pseudo-section reveals moderate conductivity between 30–100 meters, pointing to shallow conductive features, possibly from localized geological contrasts. Also, toward the end of the traverse the conductivity decreases (Fig. 2e). Traverse Six shows sharp Fraser fluctuations between +120% and -200%, with a strong positive peak near 100 meters and a deep negative anomaly around 170 meters. The Karous-Hjelt section highlights a high-conductivity zone from 80–130 meters at depths of 10–30 meters, bordered by resistive zones from 140–170 meters (Fig. 2f). These patterns indicate a complex subsurface with varying lithology and moisture content. In Traverse Seven, Fraser responses fluctuate up to $\pm 200\%$, with notable anomalies around 60–100 meters and near 190 meters. The Karous-Hjelt section confirms deep conductive zones between 80–140 meters, while both ends of the traverse are more resistive (Fig. 2g). This indicates structural or lithological variations along the traverse. Traverse Eight (ICT 1) exhibits both positive and negative Fraser peaks (-160% to +120%), corresponding with strong red (resistive) and blue-green (conductive) areas in the Karous-Hjelt section (Fig. 2h). Particularly, a sign of significant conductive zone appears between 60–160 meters, reaching depths of about 30 meters, indicating potential structural discontinuities or fluid-saturated zones. Traverse Nine (ICT 2) shows lateral conductivity contrasts with Fraser variations from -85% to +90%, especially between 55–80 meters (Fig. 2i). The Karous-Hjelt section of the same traverse reveals a prominent conductive zone from 60–120 meters at depths of 15–30 meters, suggesting saturated clays or other conductive features. Traverse Ten (ICT 3) displays Fraser fluctuations between -60% and +60%, with a notable conductive peak at 100 meters (Fig. 2j). This corresponds with a red zone on the Karous-Hjelt image at around 20 meters depth. Cooler colors between 130–160 meters suggest more resistive zones, pointing to contrasting subsurface materials. Traverse Eleven (Junior staff Quarters 1) reveals potential groundwater contamination through negative Fraser anomalies between 75–115 meters and 145–165 meters (Fig. 2k). These are supported by blue-green zones in the Karous-Hjelt section at depths of -10 to -30 meters, indicating possible saturated or

Figure 2. VLF-EM real component across traverse 1 (a) Admin block (b) Fac. Physical Science 1 (c) Fac. Physical Science 2 (d) Fac. Physical Science 3

very high concentrations. Such elevated iron values may not pose acute toxicity but can cause taste problems, staining, and, in the case of Admin block, suggest possible geogenic enrichment or contamination that could lead to long-term health issues if consumed continuously. Copper levels were consistently low (0.018–0.071 mg/L) across both boreholes and reservoirs and therefore pose no health risk. In contrast, arsenic levels were critically high in all samples, ranging from 2.837 to 3.320 mg/L, far above the WHO limit of 0.01 mg/L. This widespread arsenic contamination in both boreholes and reservoirs represents a severe public health hazard, as prolonged consumption is linked to cancers, cardiovascular diseases, and skin disorders. Lead concentrations also exceeded the safe limit of 0.01 mg/L in most cases. Boreholes at Fac of physical science (0.029 mg/L), Male Hostel (0.027 mg/L), and Junior staffs quarters (0.013 mg/L), along with reservoirs at Fac of physical science (0.027 mg/L), Male hostel (0.039 mg/L), Fac of Agric (0.189 mg/L), and Admin block (0.023 mg/L), contained unsafe levels, while only the Fac of Eng. borehole (0.003 mg/L) was within the limit. The Fac of Eng. reservoir (0.189 mg/L) is particularly alarming as such a high level of lead poses serious neurological and developmental risks, especially for children. Chromium levels in both boreholes and reservoirs remained within the WHO guideline of 0.05 mg/L (0.001–0.033 mg/L), indicating no associated risk. Overall, while zinc, cadmium, copper, and chromium were within safe limits, the elevated levels of iron, the widespread presence of lead, and the alarmingly high arsenic concentrations in both borehole and reservoir samples across locations highlight significant health concerns and render the water unsafe for direct human consumption.

Table 1. Statistical values for the heavy metals variables in samples

Parameters	WHO Standard	NSDBQ Standard	Fac. Phy Sci. (B 1)	Hostel (B 1)	Fac. Eng. (B 1)	Fac. Agric (B 1)	JS Quarters (B 1)	Fac. Phy PHS (R2)	Hostel (R2)	ENG (R2)
Zn	NS	NS	0.052 + 0.006	0.065 + 0.001	0.045 + 0.009	0.042 + 0.002	0.022 + 0.004	0.065 + 0.002	0.079 + 0.003	0.033 + 0.001
Cd	0.005	0.003	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND
Fe	0.3	0.3	0.210 + 0.003	2.176 + 0.009	0.136 + 0.003	2.808 + 0.006	2.996 + 0.054	2.176 + 0.009	0.192 + 0.001	3.937 + 0.001
Cu	1	1	0.050 + 0.001	0.028 + 0.001	0.026 + 0.006	0.021 + 0.002	0.018 + 0.0004	0.028 + 0.001	0.071 + 0.008	0.022 + 0.001
As	0.05	NS	2.956 + 0.378	2.837 + 0.173	2.963 + 0.156	3.249 + 0.425	3.206 + 0.205	2.837 + 0.174	3.056 + 2.573	3.260 + 0.001
Pb	2	NS	0.029 + 0.003	0.027 + 0.009	0.003 + 0.0001	0.015 + 0.001	0.013 + 0.004	0.027 + 0.001	0.039 + 0.006	0.016 + 0.001
Cr	NS	NS	0.002 + 0.001	0.002 + 0.001	0.033 + 0.021	0.001 + 0.002	0.005 + 0.002	0.002 + 0.001	0.004 + 0.001	0.001 + 0.001

The concentration and the alkalinity of water indicate the pH level range between 6.18 to 7.6 with temperature range between 27 to 30 °C (Fig 3). This to notice that the pH is within the permissible or neutral points while the temperature is below the standard room temperature that is permissible limit for the potable ground water in the study area (WHO, 2004; Wasiu and Abdulakdri, 2022; Olasunknmi et al., 2023). The turbidity is higher in bore holes particularly in junior staff quarters with value of 5.2 NTU, this value is above the WHO permissible limit and this may result or cause the shield of microorganism from the disinfection while the turbidity is low in the faculty of Agric borehole with value of 0.2 NTU which within the permissible range of drinking water under the WHO guidelines. However, the reservoir record low values compare to the boreholes with value range between 0.8 to 4.1 NTU, also the turbidity is in concordance with the acceptable range started by WHO and the NSDWQ. The electrical conductivity test obtained i.e. the water ionic content were range from 102 to 199 µS/cm, with higher value of 199 recorded at Faculty of physical science borehole and the low value of 102 obtained at faculty of Agric bore hole. Also, the water conductivity is below the accepted range that <1500 µS/cm for drinking water. Generally, all other parameters observed will not affect the water quality in the area (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Representation of the in situ physical parameters of water sample obtained from hand dug wells and boreholes within the selected location

The concentration of heavy metals (Zn, Cd, Fe, Cu, As, Pb, and Cr) in borehole (B/H) and reservoir (RES) samples across the study locations is shown in (Figure 4) illustrates. Zinc, copper, and chromium were consistently low across all sites (P/Science, M/Hostel, Faculty of Engineering, Faculty of Agriculture, J. Quarters, and Admin), remaining within WHO permissible limits and posing no health concern. Cadmium, which is highly toxic, was not detected in any sample, which is a positive outcome. In contrast, iron, arsenic, and lead displayed elevated concentrations in several sites. Iron exceeded the WHO limit of 0.3 mg/L in boreholes at M/Hostel, Faculty of Engineering, and Faculty of Agriculture, as well as in reservoirs at Admin and J. Quarters, which may lead to taste problems, staining, and long-term exposure risks. Arsenic concentrations were consistently high across both boreholes and reservoirs in all locations, far surpassing the WHO guideline of 0.01 mg/L, representing a widespread and critical health hazard. Lead was also above the permissible limit of 0.01 mg/L in most sites, with particularly concerning levels in the Faculty of Engineering reservoir and the Admin reservoir, both of which pose severe neurological and developmental risks, especially for children. Overall, the figure highlights that while zinc, copper, cadmium, and chromium remain safe across all sampling points, the widespread contamination by arsenic and lead, along with elevated iron levels at specific sites such as M/Hostel, Faculty of Engineering, Faculty of Agriculture, J. Quarters, and Admin, makes both borehole and reservoir water unsafe for direct human consumption in many locations.

Figure 4. Representation of the heavy metals examined from bore hole and reservoir

3.4 Physiochemical analysis

The results of the independent samples t-test comparing water quality parameters between boreholes and reservoirs at six locations within KSUSTA in Table 1 revealed that, except for nitrate concentration, there were no statistically significant differences between the two water sources. Specifically, temperature ($t = -0.03$, $p = 0.976$), conductivity ($t = 0.005$, $p = 0.996$), pH ($t = -0.521$, $p = 0.607$), hardness ($t = 0.200$, $p = 0.843$), sulphate ($t = -1.148$, $p = 0.267$), and turbidity ($t = -0.011$, $p = 0.991$) were comparable between borehole and reservoir water. However, nitrate levels differed significantly ($t = -2.731$, $p = 0.0119$), indicating that one source contained notably higher nitrate concentrations than the other. This finding suggests that while most water quality indicators are consistent across sources, nitrate contamination may require targeted investigation and management to ensure compliance with health and safety standards (Table 2).

Table 2. Independent Samples Test Equal variances not assumed

Variable	Levene F	Levene Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2 tailed)	Mean Diff.	Std. Error Diff.	95% CI Lower	95% CI Upper
Temperature	0.057	0.814	-0.030	26.945	0.976	-0.557	18.545	-38.612	37.498
Conductivity	2.186	0.151	0.005	23.636	0.996	0.059	11.045	-22.756	22.873
pH	0.002	0.966	-0.521	25.902	0.607	-0.057	0.109	-0.280	0.167
Hardness	1.973	0.172	0.200	23.624	0.843	1.315	6.564	-12.243	14.874
Nitrate	0.000	0.998	-2.731	23.179	0.012	-0.085	0.031	-0.150	-.0021
Sulphate	9.489	0.005	-1.148	16.565	0.267	-0.023	0.020	-0.066	0.019
Turbidity	1.705	0.203	-0.011	22.164	0.991	-0.006	0.511	-1.066	1.055

The mean values and standard deviation (SD) of the selected physicochemical parameters for water samples obtained from borehole (BH) reservoir (Res) were presented (Table 3). The parameters measured include temperature, electrical conductivity, pH, hardness, nitrate, sulphate and turbidity. The result show that both borehole and reservoir samples have similar conductivity and turbidity values, while slight variations exist in hardness, pH, nitrate, and sulphate concentration (Table 3).

Table 3. Mean and standard deviation of physicochemical parameters (BH) and reservoir (Res) water samples

Sample Type	Temp (mean)	Temp (SD)	Cond. (mean)	Cond. (SD)	pH (mean)	pH (SD)	Hardness (mean)	Hardness (SD)	Nitrate (Mean)	Nitrate (SD)	Sulphate (Mean)	Sulphate (SD)	Turbidity (Mean)	Turbidity (SD)
BH	52.248	47.008	156.179	33.827	7.040	0.31	93.371	20.108	0.143	0.097	0.113	0.022	2.014	1.618
BH	52.248	47.008	156.179	33.827	7.040	0.31	93.371	20.108	0.143	0.097	0.113	0.022	2.014	1.618

In figure 5, the concentrations of chemical parameters, including total suspended solids (TSS), chloride (CL), dissolved oxygen (DO), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and total hardness (T/H) in borehole (B/H) and reservoir (RES) water across different sampling locations were presented. The figure shows that BOD levels are generally the most elevated parameter, especially in the Engineering reservoir, where it peaks above 30 mg/L, which is far higher than the WHO permissible limit of 5 mg/L for drinking water. Such elevated BOD indicates a high load of organic matter and possible microbial activity, posing a serious concern for water quality and public health. Dissolved oxygen values vary across sites, with moderate levels observed; however, since the WHO recommends at least 5 mg/L to sustain aquatic life and prevent anaerobic conditions, lower DO in some reservoirs suggests deteriorating water quality. Chloride concentrations are consistently higher in reservoirs compared to boreholes, and although WHO permits up to 250 mg/L, elevated levels in reservoirs reflect possible contamination from waste discharge or surface runoff, which, if unchecked, could render the water unsuitable for consumption. Total hardness values appear moderate, with some reservoirs (e.g., Faculty of Agriculture and Admin block) showing higher levels than boreholes. While WHO permits up to 500 mg/L for hardness, higher values can cause scaling in pipes and affect taste. TSS values are generally low but are slightly elevated in reservoirs compared to boreholes, indicating greater exposure to surface inputs and potential for turbidity issues. Also, the pattern suggests that reservoirs generally have higher chemical loads than boreholes, with particularly elevated BOD and chloride concentrations that exceed or approach safe limits, making reservoirs more vulnerable to contamination, while boreholes appear relatively safer and more compliant with drinking water standards.

Figure 5. Representation of the chemical parameters examined in the water samples. borehole water and reservoir, Conc, concentration; T.H, total hardness; DO, dissolved oxygen; BOD, biochemical oxygen demand; TDS, total dissolved solids; CL, chloride TSS, total suspended solid.

4.0 CONCLUSION

The integrated interpretation of VES and VLF-EM results across the study area reveals significant subsurface heterogeneity, with clearly defined zones of high conductivity and low resistivity, particularly at VES 1 to 7, VES 11, and VES 12, and along corresponding VLF traverses such as Traverse One, Two, Four, Five, Six, Seven, Eleven, Twelve, and Thirteen. These anomalies, observed consistently in both methods, suggest saturated fractures or conductive geological formations that may serve as potential pathways for fluid movement and revealed a good ground water potential location that a borehole can be drill. However, no anthropogenic activities in the that vicinity, such as septic systems, refuse dumps, or other pollution sources, the conductive zones are more likely attributed to natural geological and hydrogeological conditions rather than active contamination. In contrast, VES 9, VES 10, and VES 13, together with VLF traverses such as traverse nine and ten, reveled high-resistivity and low-conductivity signatures, indicating relatively dry and resistive subsurface conditions. The result from the physicochemical analysis shows that while zinc, cadmium, copper, and chromium remain within WHO permissible limits and pose no immediate concern, elevated levels of iron, arsenic, and lead were detected in borehole and reservoir samples across several locations. This causes as a result of combination of geological processes(rock, water interaction, redox condition), also sedimentary aquifers rich in ironstone, shale or sulfide rich rocks can leach metals and human activities such as use of arsenic based pesticides/herbicides and phosphate fertilizers that may contain (Cd, Pb and As) as impurities and waste disposal. Iron concentrations were particularly high in boreholes at Male Hostel, Faculty of Agric, and

Junior staff Quarters, as well as in the Admin block and Fac of Agric reservoirs, which may cause taste issues, staining, and reduce water acceptability for long-term use. Lead levels exceeded permissible limits in boreholes at Fac of physical Science, male hostel, and junior staff quarters, and in reservoirs at Fac of physical science, Male hostel, Admin block, Fac of Agric, and especially the Fac of Engineering reservoir, where values were notably high, however, the interaction between water and rock which can mobilize lead into drinking water. Arsenic was consistently elevated across all boreholes and reservoirs in the study area, requiring closer monitoring and control. Generally, these findings may require water treatment, regular monitoring, and awareness creation, ensuring a safe and sustainable supply for the KSUSTA community. It is recommended that hydrogeological validation through borehole drilling and water quality testing be carried out to confirm the nature of the conductive zones. Continuous monitoring and periodic geophysical surveys are also advised to track any future changes in subsurface conditions and to ensure sustainable groundwater resource management.

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Author contribution

Conceptual framework, investigation, data processing and analysis, U.Z. Magawata while editing, rewire of the manuscript was done by all the author and data acquisition and review by M.M. lawal.

Declaration

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Appendix 1

Appendix 2

Appendix 3

